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Customer Satisfaction on Service Quality of Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the customers' satisfaction at Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services in Balanga City, Bataan to sustain and continually improve the customer satisfaction and quality service to the community. The study utilized purposive sampling with a 537 customer-respondents in the transport terminals. A descriptive research design was used in this study to establish the difference between profile variables, travelling information, customers' satisfaction and quality service. Independent t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to test the hypotheses. Results showed that there is a significant difference between all the variables of the dimension of the customer satisfaction and quality service at Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services. The customers' satisfaction dimensions: reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness established strong differences with the quality service. The rating given by the respondents on the customers' satisfaction rendered at Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services and the quality service is very satisfactory. Finally, the policy and practical implications of the study findings to improve bus service performance. This paper also proposes an enhancement plan for sustaining customer satisfaction of Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services.

Keywords: Business education, Customer Satisfaction, Quality Service, Descriptive Research Design, Empathy and Responsiveness

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INTRODUCTION

Transportation is an integral part of modern life. Public transport is a shared passenger transportation service available to the general public. It plays a crucial part in sustaining and increasing economic growth. A well-developed transport network facility reflects the integration and interdependence of the different sectors by aiding the quick and adequate movement of men and materials (Transport and Communication Roads and Bridges, 2023). It is vital for the development of various sectors of the economy in a developing country.

In countries like the Philippines, road transport demands a higher priority since it forms the backbone of the passenger mobility system and is the principal carrier of the developmental process from one part of the country to another. The more extensive and continuous production in any sector, the greater the need for transport facilities. Transport development helps to open up remote regions and resources for production and helps in fuller utilization of resources. The Philippines, a developing country in the Southeast Asian region, depends on the public transportation sector to link cities and provinces with each other. Public utility buses are considered as one of the commonly used types of public utility vehicle being utilized by the

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commuters and passengers that is suited for medium and long-distance travels both in rural and urban places in the country (Tindowen 2015). According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, there are 31,665 Public Utility Buses being registered plying throughout the archipelago in the year 2013. There are two classifications of buses in the Philippines: Public Utility Buses and Public Utility minibuses. Public Utility Buses have a seating capacity of 50 and above excluding driver and conductor while Public Utility Minibus has a seating capacity of 30 - 49 excluding driver and conductor. Both buses have fixed routes, regular, limited-stop, or express. Route travel can be seen on cardboards displayed on the bus' windshield. Bus ventilation has a Regular/Non-airconditioned and air-conditioned bus. The bus fare was based on distance or zonal as authorized by the Land Transportation Franchising and Regulatory Board (LTFRB) (Department Order NO. 97-097).

In the Philippines, Region III, specifically in the province of Balanga City, Bataan, many modes of transportation are available. Buses, jeepneys, and vans are readily available for use in getting around the city. It is a reality in the city with the presence of public utility buses and public utility minibuses, which are usually plying to serve and connect within the municipalities of Balanga City, Bataan. Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services is vital in transportation in Balanga and Olongapo. Usually, public utility buses offer services like air-conditioned and Regular/Non-airconditioned type of buses to satisfy the needs of their commuters and passengers in terms of safety and comfort. Some research and articles stipulate that small feeders or minibuses are unsafe for passengers and commuters (Najimi, 2009; Hui, 2013; Agirab, 2015; Jandaly, 2013). However, despite the warnings and measures to the commuters and passengers, many still prefer to ride on a public transportation bus primarily because of its cheap fare compared to other public utility vehicles such as taxis and vans. Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services usually do not go to the city centers. They stop at their designated bus terminals.

Service quality is recognized as one of the important areas on which public organizations including transportation services are focusing in present times (Ancarani & Capaldo, 2001). Service quality is generally visualized as the sum of customer perceptions of the service experience (Safi & Alagha, 2020). The difference between service quality and satisfaction is perceived service quality is a global judgment, or attitude, relating to the superiority of the service. Whereas satisfaction is related to the specific transaction (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Customers form service expectations from many sources, such as past experiences, word of mouth, and advertising. In general, customers compare the perceived services with the expected service. If the perceived service falls below the expected service, customers are dissatisfied and if the perceived service quality is above the expected level, it creates satisfied customers (Vu, 2021). Marketers need to understand that customers are more than mere consumers of service quality output; they are co-producers of the quality process. According to Parasuraman et al., (1988) service quality has become a significant differentiator and the most powerful competitive weapon (Arora & Garg, 2007), which many service organizations possess. Successful companies add benefits to their offering that not only satisfy customers but surprise and delight. Delighting the customers is a matter of exceeding expectations (Kim & Matilla, 2002).

Expectations can be formed before or during the delivery of a service. They reflect beliefs as to what will or should happen (Coye, 2004). Customer expectations may be defined as the desires and wants of consumers and the feel what a service provider should offer rather than would offer. All the definitions of service quality focus on meeting customer's needs and requirements and how well the service delivered matches the customer's expectations. Customer perception is "the process by which an individual selects, organizes and interprets information inputs to create a meaningful picture of the world". Perceptions of a service are a complex series of judgments formed during or at the end of the experience

Customer satisfaction is "the result of customers' assessment of a service based on comparing their perceptions of service delivery with their prior expectations (Zhang, 2009). Customers develop a particular

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set of expectations based on a variety of inputs. They consider their previous experiences with services in general and each specific service they have encountered (William et al., 2016). Customers also develop expectations when they hear about services from others. If you hear that your friend was delighted with public bus transport services, you are more likely to expect that same level of service if you ride there. Customers also form expectations based on service provider's advertisements and promotions. The quest for service quality has been an essential strategic component for service firms like buses attempting to succeed and survive in today's competitive environment (Muthupandian, & Vijayakumar, 2012). The SERVQUAL model focuses on the difficulty in ensuring a high quality of service for all customers in all situations. SERVQUAL methodology is an analytical approach for evaluating the difference between customers' expectations and perceptions of quality.

Over the last few years, companies have gradually focused on service quality and customer satisfaction (Mussa, 2022). This strategy is profitable for companies and customers, particularly transit agencies and passengers. An improvement in the supplied service quality can attract further users. This fact could resolve many problems (e.g., helping to reduce traffic congestion, air and noise pollution, and energy consumption) because individual transport would be used less (Sezhian et al., 2011). For this reason, developing techniques for customer satisfaction analysis is necessary. These techniques allow the critical aspects of the supplied services to be identified and customer satisfaction to be increased (Mussa, 2022).

This study is conducted to assess the quality service of public transportation buses plying in Balanga City, Bataan, to improve and sustain the quality service at Balanga Olongapo Transport Services. Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services, among the few profit-making public bus transport organizations in Balanga City, Bataan, Philippines, is taken as the study to analyze the existing customers' expectations and perceptions. It is one of the competitive public bus transport organizations in the region; they are still to reach the desired level of passenger mode share that will enable service providers and policymakers to address needs within the public transport environment adequately and to provide sustainable mobility solutions to the commuters in Balanga City, Bataan, Philippines.

Service quality is created at each step of the process, and it is essential to understand customer preferences and expectations from the services. Customer expectations are evaluated based on five key quality requirements and analyzed using statistical methods to understand their relative importance to a target customer chosen for a survey. Policies, management regulations, registrations, and control systems applied by the Authorities are the most critical aspects in this direction. However, more detailed studies of operational aspects of public transportation may contribute significantly to its sustainability and efficiency. Thus, this study aids policymakers, researchers, and the government in improving the various quality aspects of Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive research design was used in this study to establish the difference between profile variables, travelling information, customer satisfaction and quality service. According to Thyer (2010) and Asio (2021), descriptive research involves conducting analyses to evaluate whether there is any relationship on variables. It entails determining how the variables are distributed and the findings are shown using chart or graph.

For purposes of this study, this describes the situation of the respondents who are customers/passengers of Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services. Furthermore, the study describes the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, civil status, and employment status. The travelling information of the respondents.

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Likewise, study describes the five dimensions of customer satisfaction based on SERVQUAL Model which are reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness that would serve as a basis for improving and sustaining the quality service of Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services.

Participants

The study was centered at Balanga City, Bataan and its current customers. Purposive sampling technique was used for the sample selection of the sample is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study (Campbell et al., 2017).

The respondents of this study were about the five hundred thirty-seven (537) customers during the fiscal year 2019. This study utilized purposive sampling in selecting respondents. The respondents were chosen purposely for this study to gather information on the customer satisfaction and quality service at said transport services. The respondents who were able to answer and return the questionnaire were included as the official respondents. The survey forms and google forms were randomly distributed to the target size of respondents within two weeks.

Through analyzing the profile of the respondent (sex, age, civil status and employment status), travelling information (purpose of travelling, frequency of riding a public transportation bus, hardest day of the week for respondents to travel, hardest time of the day for respondents to travel and type of bus commonly on board), customer satisfaction (reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness) and quality service, the areas for improvement could be easily determined to sustain high level of customer satisfaction and enhancement of quality service delivery at Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services.

Instrumentation

The research instrument was adapted from Urban Bus Transport Service Quality and Sustainable Development: Understanding the Gaps, by Meghna et al., (2013). The first part contains the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, civil status and employment status. The second part is to identify customers travelling information. The third part of the questionnaire assessed the level of customers' satisfaction of public transportation buses and the last part was the overall quality service of public transportation buses. The format of the questionnaire is in Likert point scale. The third and fourth section is about expectations and overall service public transportation buses. The respondents' answer will be measured on a four-point scale ranging from "4 = Strongly Agree" to "1 = Strongly Disagree". There is a total of 35 structured and closed ended questions. The survey was conducted within two weeks with 537 passengers and commuters as its respondents. The questionnaire personally distributed to the respondents and retrieved it immediately.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered were tabulated, organized in processed through IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences Statistics version 25 (IBM SPSS Statistics 25). The following statistical tools were used to treat the specific problems raised in the study: Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used to organize the profile of the respondents which includes sex, age, civil status, and employment status. Weighted Mean was used to assess the customer satisfaction in terms of reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness and the overall quality service of public transportation buses. T-Test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for independent sample were used to test the significant difference when grouped according to the respondents' profile variables and customer satisfaction in terms of reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness. The following rules were adopted in hypothesis testing decisions. If the probability value is equal or less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the research hypothesis; and if the probability value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

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Ethical Consideration

Consent form was included on the survey questionnaire that were handed out to the respondents. The respondents may participate and withdraw at any time without costing them anything. The research study also took consideration of the Data Privacy Act or the Republic Act 10173 which ensures the privacy of the information given to the researcher by the respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section contains the data presentations and interpretation of results with the aid of reviewed literature and studies.

Profile of the Respondents

Sex. Out of 537 respondents, 292 or 54.4% are female while only 245 or 45.6% are male. Based on Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) Quick Stat Bataan as of June 2018, there are 52,076 females and 40,193 male residents in Bataan. (Source: 2000 and 2010 Census of Population and Housing (CPH) 2007 and 2015 Census of Population (POPCEN)). There is an increasing rate of female passengers than male passengers using Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services.

Age. Various age ranges of the respondents are from below 14 as the lowest to 90 and above. There are 191 respondents or 35.6% who fall under the range of 20-29 which represents the highest respondents which means that the age group is most frequently passengers of Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services. Next highest are those respondents who are age ranges from 30-39 corresponding to 17.7%. The lowest number of frequencies was the age bracket 80-89 with 0% which seemed to be the least of passengers of Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services. According to the report on Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) Bataan Quick Stat as of June 2018, there are 64.4% who fall under the range of 15-64 which represents the highest age group and the lowest number of frequency bracket fall under the range of 65 and over corresponding to 3.8% (2010).

Civil Status. This reveals that majority of the respondents are single while the least belongs to annulled/separated. Out of 537 respondents, 286 or 53.3% are single. Only 224 or 41.7% are married while 24 or 4.5% are widower and 3 or .6% are annulled or separated. Based on the report on Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) Quick Stat Bataan as of June 2018, there are 250,455 single, 243,688 married, 26,346 widower and 80,982 annulled/separated.

Employment Status. This reveals that majority of the respondents are employed while the least belongs to self-employed. There are 231 respondents or 43% who fall under employed which represents the highest respondent. This is followed by unemployed with 160 respondents or 29.8% and 146 or 27.2% who fall under self-employed which shows the lowest respondents. In the paper of Lorenzo et al., (2021) most of their respondents were regular employees which contradicts the current findings. From the October 2015 census of Philippine Statistics Office, women employment rate is higher than men unemployment rate. It is for this reason many of the female respondents patronizes the public transportation buses of the Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services.

Purpose of Travelling

Majority of the respondents are employees travelling for their workplace while the least belongs to students going to school. Out of 537 respondents, 220 or 41% are travelling to work. Only 65 or 12.1% are travelling to school while 170 or 31.7% are going home and 82 or 15.3% for others. According to the study it seems that the purpose of travelling is connected with building social relationships, opportunities to learn and

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grow, and commitment. It gives us the chance to be truly engaged in an activity, to develop new skills and go in different places or destinations. It brings us closer to ourselves and others.

Customer Satisfaction on Public Transportation Busses

Reliability. Passengers are agreed in the items the information about availability of bus and the schedule timetable for buses. Sustaining and continuing enhancement in customer satisfaction by providing the service right the first time is necessary. Public transport must be predictable in terms of travel time, waiting time, and schedule. Commuters will benefit from a fixed dispatch time and short intervals between vehicles during peak demand periods, as they need not wait long for the PUV to arrive. Operating hours for a route shall also be responsive to the needs of visitors, night students, and workers who require late night travel. The reliability and performance consistency of service facilities, service itself and provider himself including rendering service on time and ability to do what the provider promised to do for customer.

Assurance. The respondents agreed that the feeling of personal safety and security is another reason for the respondents why they are riding on public transportation buses. They feel secured when riding public transportation buses because the size is quite bigger than other public utility vehicles and it is easy for them to escape from the vehicle when emergency case or situation will happen. In addition, another reason for the passengers for riding a public transportation bus is that it is suitable for those with luggage. This is attributed to the fact that public utility buses have a spacious compartment to be used for storage of large and heavy things and equipment. Assurance is having employee who are knowledgeable, courteous and trustworthy.

Tangibility. The respondents agreed on the tangibility dimension of the busses from the operator. Buses and Bus stops are clean, ventilation is very comfortable, and presence of entertainment equipment. Also, respondents enjoy watching films and listening to old songs while they are on the trip. Bus stops and stations shall be adequately lit at night for security. Designated location of stops, pick-up, and drop-off points with adequate facilities shall be provided to facilitate convenient boarding and alighting of passengers. Customer satisfaction based on tangibility could be further achieved by Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services through improvements and maintaining its facilities.

Empathy. The item bus is user friendly persons with disability, pregnant women and senior citizen got the highest assessment on satisfaction. However, the item being assessed as the lowest by the passengers is the availability of first aid in every bus. It further shows that Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services need to further improve the availability of first aid and special needs of its passenger to achieve customer satisfaction. Public transport must be available in every community, with accessibility for all segments of society, including senior citizens and persons with disabilities. The vehicle is fitted with comfortable seats where passengers are able to relax, rest, and be productive during the journey. For buses that permit standing passengers, the number of standing passengers must not exceed five (5) persons per square meter of the available standing space.

Responsiveness. The respondents rated agree on this specific dimension. Among the items under this area, the items bus companies always inform people of availability of services and changes in prices in advance and bus stops are conveniently located got the highest assessment on satisfaction. The drivers and conductors can answer passengers' questions in short time, they response completely and reasonably to passenger complaints. This implies that bus operators and drivers generally have good communication skills that they easily build connections and relationships with their passengers. The commitment to work by employees including honor, glory, pride, satisfaction and employee's diligence on his duty and work. Rendering service and communicate with customers in a way that he/she understands, including clarity, complete and correct oral and written information given to the customer. Quick and timeliness of services including service ability to respond promptly to customer wants with minimal waiting.

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Quality Service. Data reveals that quality service of public transportation buses per unit section were rated agree in all terms to wit: (1) “Providing services at the promised time” (Mean Score 2.97); (2) “Safe and Security Service” (Mean Score 2.98); (3) “Employees have the knowledge to answer customer questions” (Mean Score 2.99); (4) “Making customer safe in every transactions” (Mean Score 2.93); (5) “Modern equipment” (Mean Score 2.91); (6) “Visually appealing facilities” (Mean Score 2.96); (7) “Give customers individual attention” (Mean Score 3.01); (8) “Reasonable Bus Fare” (Mean Score 2.97); (9) “Employees understand the needs of their customers” (Mean Score 2.94) and (10) “Bus companies always inform what is available or prohibit services”.

This denotes that Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services is delivering quality service and passengers agreed with its services. The table shows the quality service being offered by Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services. This indicator includes bus companies give special care for persons with disability, pregnant women and senior citizen got the highest quality service. There are friendly and reasonable answers of bus operators to passenger’s inquiries and concern.

The table also revealed that the passengers are riding in public transportation bus is due to its cheap ride fare. They end up riding on public transportation bus to save money. Also, results of the interview revealed that there is a difference of PhP 10.00 – PhP 20.00 on the fare of public transportation buses from other modes of public transportation such as public utility van and public utility jeepneys. The latest fare matrix approved by the Land Transportation Franchising and Regulatory Board (LTFRB) indicated that the minimum fare for public utility buses ranges from PhP 9.00-PhP 10.00 for the first five kilometers with 0.20 – PhP 1.75 for every succeeding kilometer.

Test of Difference on the variables of the study

Profile Variables. There are no significant differences on the profile variables in the customer satisfaction of public transportation buses at Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services.

Reliability and Profile Variables. There is no sufficient example or evidence to prove the significance differences in the customer satisfaction with the above-mentioned profile variables. According to Singh et al., (2023), it is essential for quality to be right the first time every time. Reliable service performance has to meet customer expectation. Service must be accomplished on time, every time in the same manner without errors. Reliability is the extent to which the service is delivered to the standards (Ramya et al., 2019).

Assurance and Profile Variables. There is no significant difference on the customer satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to the mentioned profile variables. Staffs are the persons who have significant role to play in determining the customers’ satisfaction. They are the persons who have direct contact with the passengers of different background needs. Courteous behavior and helpful attitude of the staff is expected to maintain the level of satisfaction of the passengers.

Tangibility and Profile Variables. There is no significant difference on the customer satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to the profile variables. Sriyam (2012) found out that most of respondents identified tangibility as the most important factor in determining satisfaction. It includes the personality and appearance. When staffs are well dressed and wear uniforms, buses are clean and well maintained the appearance impresses customers who feel more confident with services. The service quality was related to the tangible behavior and appearance of employees and buses.

Empathy and Profile Variables. There is no significant difference on the customer satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to the profile variables. Any passenger, young or old, male or female, educated or non-educated, would expect the bus operators to provide a comfortable travel. Good seating arrangements, proper ventilation, sufficient space inside the bus and proper lighting are the aspects that may provide comforts to passengers which in turn, enhance the level of customer satisfaction.

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Responsiveness and Profile Variables. There is no significant difference on the customer satisfaction when respondents are grouped according to the profile variables. Punctuality and Regularity is a criterion for the efficient operation of buses. If the bus operator does not follow punctuality and regularity, it may cause great hardship to the passenger to go to their place of destination. Regularity must adhere in the sense that there should be no cancellation of trips, immediate action on complaints, which may increase the level of customer satisfaction.

Lived Experiences of customers-respondent in the services of the public transportation buses

The following responses were taken and conducted while waiting for buses for the trip to Olongapo City to Balanga City and vice-versa. Some have mentioned that most of the time they find hard time to commute most especially during rainy seasons and rush hours. So, despite and in spite of there are some occasions they rather stand all throughout instead of waiting for a bus to arrive because it saves more time rather than waiting in vain considering that the terminal is not that much conducive to stay. Most of the respondents would like that the bus operators must have a tangible program especially on the schedules of trips to Balanga City and Olongapo City vice versa. The development of buses must be considered especially to non-air-conditioned to have a rightful satisfaction of the commuters. Lastly, they prefer to have a ride in these buses because it is cheaper compared to other public transport accordingly.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the findings the following conclusions are presented:

1. The result of the five dimensions of customer satisfaction based on the SERVQUAL model show a descriptive rating of agree. Reliability (2.90) and Tangibility (2.87) show further improvements to attain an increased customer satisfaction at Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services, while Assurance (2.92), Empathy (2.91) and Responsiveness (2.91) need to be sustained to achieve highest level customer satisfaction.
2. Quality Service at Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services showed high rating results but not perfect or highest score rating. Provision to address long waiting time is usually the problem encountered by passengers in riding local minibuses.
3. There is no significant difference in the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, civil status and employment status.
4. A proposed enhancement plan on customer satisfaction consists of various strategies and guide to the Transport Services is hereby presented as an output of the study. The reliable and sustainable communication system between service provider and service consumer is one of the best means of retaining customer in such a competitive business. Substantial evidence is now available that customers' perceptions of service quality performance of specific acts are very predictive of their overall satisfactions and willingness to use the service again, if needed.

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were endorsed:

1. Since Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services is mostly catering to a young legal age group, personnel must adjust to their needs by using simple words in giving instructions and avoid unfamiliar words. Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services must be responsive to their queries and provide extra assistance for their transaction. The public bus transportation system should use user-friendly printed material (e.g. area-based timetables, posters and brochures) which customers relate too. Electronic media should also be used to greater effect (e.g. a comprehensively detailed website). This will address issues around

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empathy and tangibles in the industry. With the high percentage of female customers, male employees must be respectful and act appropriately at all times towards female customers to assure them that they are safe.

2. Further sustainability and innovation on Tangibility can be attained by continuous monitoring of minor and major repairs. The reliability of the bus service should be sustained in three ways: Firstly, a consistently aligned set of factors, processes and standards that can define timely routing should be developed. Secondly, there should be regular maintenance of the fleet as well as readily available spare equipment and parts. Thirdly, new technologies (e.g. Global Positioning/tracking system) should be introduced and maintained to control routes and timings. Changes in time and prices should be communicated quickly to customers. On empathy, personnel must undergo seminar or workshop to show genuine interest and sustaining full attention when serving a customer. On responsiveness, personnel are recommended to provide prompt service. Sustaining the assurance training and upgrading personnel's knowledge is recommended to build the personnel's confidence in handling customer service.
3. There should be greater interaction with present as well as potential customers with a view to understanding their needs more clearly.
4. Regular surveys should be conducted and customer complaints, fully analyzed. Staff members need to be made aware of customer feedback as well as complaints so that the necessary actions can be taken.
5. The Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services is recommended to maintain the customer satisfaction dimensions on Empathy and Responsiveness by attendance of the employee to organized seminars and workshops on practicing empathy towards clients. Employees' seminar is highly recommended to consider.
6. The proposed enhancement plan on customer satisfaction consists of various strategy and guide to the Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services to further improve and sustain its customer satisfaction to the services to achieve excellence in its overall operation. Detailed policies and procedures should be developed so that the variability in customer treatment is reduced.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study assessed the customer satisfaction of Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services in achieving improvement and sustaining quality service of public transportation buses. It is delimited to the following; (1) personal profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, civil status and employment status, (2) travelling information in terms of purpose of travelling, frequency of riding a public transportation bus, hardest day of the week for respondents to travel, hardest time of the day for respondents to travel and type of bus commonly on board, (3) customer satisfaction of public transportation buses include: reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness (4) quality service of public transportation buses. Distribution of survey questionnaire was conducted in this study in order to gather data and validate the responses of the respondents during the administration of the questionnaire. The present customers of the Balanga-Olongapo Transport Services on February 2019 are the respondents of the study.

REFERENCES

- Agarib, A. (2013). Minibuses are the most dangerous vehicles on the road. <http://www.khaleejtimes.com/nation/transport/drive-finds-mini-buses-most-dangerous-vehicle-on-roads>

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- Al Jandaly, B. (2015). Minibuses to be banned from transporting school children. <http://gulfnews.com/news/uae/minibuses-set-to-be-banned-from-transporting-schoolchildren-in-dubai-1.1197820>
- Amesho, K. (2016). Critical assessment of Public Transportation System (PTS) and its implication on environmental economics through service delivery. *Environmental Economics*. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ee.07\(4\).2016.04](https://doi.org/10.21511/ee.07(4).2016.04)
- Asio, J.M. (2021). Research Designs in the New Normal: A Brief Overview. *Academia Letters*, Article 2596. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL2596>
- Ancarani, A., & Capaldo, G. (2001). Management of standardised public services: a comprehensive approach to quality assessment. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 11(5), 331-341. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09604520110404059>
- Arora, P., & Garg, A. (2007). Service Quality in Punjab Telecom Circle. *Icfai Journal of Services Marketing*, 5(2), 19-40.
- Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., Bywaters, D., & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive sampling: complex or simple? Research case examples. *Journal of research in nursing: JRN*, 25(8), 652–661. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>
- Coye, R. W. (2004). Managing customer expectations in the service encounter. *International Journal of service industry management*, 15(1), 54-71. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09564230410523330>
- Department Order No. 97-1097 (1997 September 29). *Providing Standard Classification for all Public Transport Conveyances*. Retrieved from https://kupdf.net/download/dotc-dept-order-no-97-1097_58fea736dc0d60cb7b959e82_pdf
- Hui, C. (2009). *The dangers of minibuses*. <https://aiyamag.wordpress.com/2013/08/12/minibuses-and-the-dangers-of-not-projecting/>
- Lorenzo, E., Paguio, D., & Asio, J. M. (2021). Budget Allocation System of a Highly Urbanized Local Government Unit in Central Luzon, Philippines. *International Journal of Humanities, Management and Social Science*, 4(2), 51-62. <https://doi.org/10.36079/lamintang.ij-humass-0402.283>
- Meghna, V., Ashish, V., Ajith, P., & Sneha, S. (2013). Urban bus transport service quality and sustainable development: understanding the gaps. In *Proceedings of 13th World Conference on Transport Research, Brazil*. <http://www.wetrans-society.com/wp-content/uploads/abstracts/rio/selected/1186.pdf>
- Mussa, M. R. (2022). *The Influence of Customer Care on Customer Satisfaction in Daladala Transportation Services in Zanzibar Town* (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania). <http://repository.out.ac.tz/id/eprint/3680>
- Muthupandian, K. S., & Vijayakumar, D. C. (2012). Measurement of passengers service quality in public transportation: servqual analysis. <https://mp.ra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/38584/>
- Najimi, A. (2005). *Minibuses not safe to carry passengers*. <http://gulfnews.com/news/uae/transport/minibuses-not-safe-to-carry-passengers-1.541610>
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A. & Berry, L.L. (1985). A conceptual model of service quality and its implication. *Journal of Marketing*, volume 49, pp. 41-50.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, Valerie A., & Berry, Leonard L. (1985). "SERVQUAL: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality," *Journal of Retailing*, volume 64 (1), pp. 12-40
- Philippine Statistics Authority (2013). *Statistics of public utility buses*. https://psa.gov.ph/sites/default/files/2013%20PY_Transportation.pdf
-

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- Ramya, N., Kowsalya, A., & Dharanipriya, K. (2019). Service quality and its dimensions. *EPR International Journal of Research & Development*, 4(2), 38-41. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333058377>
- Safi, F. O., & Alagha, M. S. (2020). The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 10(8), 767-787. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.10.08.2020.p10497>
- Sezhian, M. V., Muralidharan, C., Nambirajan, T., & Deshmukh, S. G. (2011). Developing a performance importance matrix for a public sector bus transport company: A case study. *Theoretical and Empirical Researches in Urban Management*, 6(3), 5-14. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/rom/terumm/v6y2011i3p5-14.html>
- Singh, V., Sharma, M. P., Jayapriya, K., Kumar, B. K., Chander, M. A. R. N., & Kumar, B. R. (2023). Service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: A comprehensive literature review. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(4S), 3457-3464. <http://dx.doi.org/10.53555/sfs.v10i4S.2218>
- Sriyam, A. L. I. N. (2010). Customer satisfaction towards service quality of front office staff at the hotel. *Master Paper Of Arts Degree In Business English For International Communication*. <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/7703900/customer-satisfaction-towards-service-quality-of->
- Thyer, B. (2010). *The handbook of social work research methods*, (2nd ed.). Florida State University USA: SAGE Publications Inc.
- Tindowen, D.J.C. (n.d.). Perceived service quality of local minibuses in Tuguegarao city, Philippines by the travelling public. *Transport and communication roads and Bridges (state sector)*. AZPDF INDIA. (2023). <https://azpdf.net/in/article/transport-and-communication-roads-and-bridges-state-sector.7616338>
- Vu. T. (2021). Service quality and its impact on customer satisfaction. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17089454.v2>
- William, O., Appiah, E. E., & Botchway, E. A. (2016). Assessment of customer expectation and perception of service quality delivery in Ghana commercial bank. *Journal of Humanity*, 4(1), 81-91. <https://doi.org/10.14724/jh.v4i1.59>
- Yao, L., Siali F., Darun, M.R. B, Ismail, M. F., (2014, September 8-10). *Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction: Rapid Kuantan in Kuantan Route, Malaysia*. Proceedings of SOCIOINT14-International Conference on Social Sciences and Humanities. Retrieved from <https://docplayer.net/64361414-Service-quality-and-customer-satisfaction-rapid-kuantan-in-kuantan-route-malaysia.html>
- Zhang, J. (2009). An investigation into guests' perceived service quality of the bed-and-breakfast and guest house market industry in the Nelson Mandela Bay area. <https://core.ac.uk/download/145048113.pdf>
-